

Risk Factors for Leishmaniasis in Residents of the Municipality of Canindé – CE: An Exploratory Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Leishmaniasis are diseases caused by protozoa of the genus *Leishmania*, which may have infections with various clinical manifestations or asymptomatic. Brazil is classified as a country with endemic transmission for this disease, considered to be neglected in the national territory. The endemic scenario is repeated in the state of Ceará, especially in the municipality of Canindé, focus of this study. The objective of the study was to analyze the risk factors for Visceral Leishmaniasis in residents of Canindé. For this, analyzes of the number of Leishmaniasis cases were obtained from the Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINANWEB) and then calculated the Relative Risk and Confidence Index. The data obtained suggests that residents of Canindé are not at imminent risk of infections caused by *Leishmania* spp., however, when compared to other regions of Brazil, they are exposed to relatively significant risks.

Additional keywords: Protozoa; Confidence index; Risk of infection; Risk factories.

RESUMO

Fatores de Risco em Residentes do Município de Canindé

Leishmanioses são doenças causadas por protozoários do gênero *Leishmania*, os quais podem causar infecções com várias manifestações clínicas ou assintomáticas. O Brasil é classificado como o país com transmissão endêmica para esta doença, considerada ser uma doença negligenciada no território nacional. O cenário endêmico é repetido no estado do Ceará, especialmente no município de Canindé, foco deste estudo. O objetivo deste estudo foi de analisar os fatores de risco para a Leishmaniose Visceral em residentes de Canindé. Para isto, análises do número de casos de Leishmanioses foram obtidos a partir do Sistema de Informação de Notificação de Doenças e então calculado o Risco Relativo Índice de Confiança. Os dados obtidos sugerem que os residentes de Canindé não possuem risco iminente de infecções causadas por *Leishmania* spp., contudo quando comparado com outras regiões do Brasil, eles estão expostos a significante risco relativo.

Palavras-chave adicionais: Protozoa; Índices de confiança; Risco de infecção; Fatores de risco.

INTRODUCTION

Leishmaniasis is a group of diseases caused by protozoa of the genus *Leishmania*, which belongs to the taxonomic class Kinetoplastea (Ferreira, 2017). These protozoa are capable

of causing diseases with multifaceted clinical manifestations, ranging from asymptomatic infections to cutaneous, mucocutaneous and visceral forms (Diogo, 2022). It is estimated that between 700,000 and 1 million new cases occur annually worldwide, with Brazil representing

more than 97% of visceral leishmaniasis cases in the Americas (WHO, 2021).

Brazil is classified among the group of 92 countries with endemic transmission and is one of the 25 countries with a high burden of the disease (Scandar, 2011). Between 1999 and 2018, more than 68,000 cases of visceral leishmaniasis (VL) and more than 460,000 cases of American tegumentary leishmaniasis (ATL) were registered in the country, with transmission occurring in 23 (Luna, 2020) of the 26 states and the Federal District.

The permanence of this endemic state can be associated with precarious survival conditions, such as difficult access to health care, poor basic sanitation conditions (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2017), frequently the mismanagement result of local politics, corruption or simply government neglect. This situation is further intensified by intense uncontrolled urbanization, which causes gradual population growth and degradation of nature, leaving these urban centers lacking the essential conditions for a healthy life (Peixoto, 2020). Therefore, population awareness and environmental intervention strategies are necessary to control parasitic diseases, in this case VL and ATL, which are neglected diseases throughout Brazil (Caldas, 2022).

In this context, this study aimed to assess the epidemiological status of ATL and VL in the city of Canindé-CE and in the State of Ceará, as well as to analyze policies and actions that aimed to promoting health and preventing leishmaniasis, with a view to reducing reported cases of VL and ATL. In addition, predictions about the risk of developing leishmaniasis in the population living in the municipality of Canindé-CE were evaluated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Visceral leishmaniasis and ATL are notifiable diseases in Brazilian territory, as established by Law 6,259 of 10/30/1975. Therefore, the study is based on a retrospective, cross-sectional model and secondary sources of patients affected by leishmaniasis obtained from the Notifiable Diseases Information System - SINANWEB (<https://portalsinan.saude.gov.br/>) made available by the Department of Informatics of the Unified Health System (DATASUS), from 2010 to 2020.

Similarly, exhaustive bibliographic analysis in Public Databases including the Virtual Health Library (VHL), PubMed and Scientific Electronic Library Online (ScieELO), using the descriptors: "leishmaniasis", "visceral leishmaniasis" and "tegumentary leishmaniasis" were carried out. For this purpose, the inclusion criteria were papers published only in Portuguese, English or Spanish and their central theme was visceral and/or tegumentary leishmaniasis.

After obtaining the data, the socio demographic profile of the cases reported for VL in residents of Canindé-CE was obtained, in which parameters such as: age group, sex, race and area of residence were computed. The correlation between the cases observed for VL in Brazil, Ceará State and Canindé-CE took into account the annual population of the analyzed territory and the incidence of cases in the same period, with a factor for determining cases per 100,000 inhabitants. Thus, we sought to establish association measures to evaluate the relationship between exposure to the risk factor and the outcome of the disease, using the Relative Risk (RR) measure (Hennekens & Buring, 1987; Kahn & Sempos, 1989). The risk factor adopted is attributed to the fact of living in Canindé, and the outcome is attributed to the development of the disease in a given period.

In order to demonstrate that the RR finding was significant, i.e. the risk factor was reflected in a real effect on the population studied, the logarithmic transformation method was used to calculate the Confidence Interval (CI) of the RR for the factor P ($p < 0.05$ (95%)), as described by Gardner & Altman (1989). The calculation assumes the approximation of data to a two-tailed normal distribution curve performed in each annual sample. Finally, the resulting value of the RR and IC for the Canindé/Ceará and Canindé/Brazil relationship was analyzed during the period from 2011 to 2020.

All collected data were organized in spreadsheets using the Excel 2016 tool present in the Microsoft Office® package, and were subsequently analyzed using the Biostatistics software, version 5.3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of VL and ATL cases in the municipality of Canindé revealed a correlated profile with a greater predominance of VL cases

in relation to ATL cases during the period 2011-2020 (Figure 1). During this period there were 53 cases of VL and 10 cases of ATL, where the annual case incidence profile maintained a pattern, with the exception of the years 2011, 2014 and 2015, in which there was an endemic peak in cases of Leishmaniasis, corresponding to around 58.5% of all cases in the period.

The State of Ceará (Figure 2) showed an opposite profile to the city of Canindé, with a higher case incidence related to ATL. Around 54.8% of Leishmaniasis cases in Ceará were ATL, however this number corresponds to only 15.8%

of cases in Canindé. In Ceará, between 2011 and 2020 there was a similarity between the number of cases of the two diseases except for the years 2012 and 2020, in which there was a greater discrepancy related to ATL cases. It is important to highlight the epidemiological scenario in 2012, which revealed the biggest difference in relation to the profiles of the city and the state.

From these analyzes we can elaborate three initial hypotheses, based on epidemiological findings.

The first related to the possible underreporting of VL cases in the municipality,

Source: Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINAN); data up to April/2022

Figure 1 - Relationship between the frequency of cases of VL and ATL in residents of Canindé, 2011-2020.

Source: Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINAN); data up to April/2022

Figure 2 - Relationship between the frequency of VL and ATL cases in Ceará, 2011-2020.

as described by Maia-Elkhoury *et al.* (2007), who identified in a study the number of cases of deaths due to VL in Brazil, in the Mortality Information System, which were not registered on SINAN in the period from 2002 to 2003, revealing the underreporting of cases, and this scenario could be repeated in the municipality on a smaller scale (Maia-Elkhoury *et al.*, 2007).

The second is related to the complexity of the clinical diagnosis of VL, as the disease presents several signs and symptoms that are common to other diseases, which are also endemic in regions where there is an incidence of Leishmaniasis (Gontijo & Melo, 2004).

Finally, the hypothesis that many *Leishmania* infections can be completely asymptomatic, however, the absence of a gold standard test makes it impossible to diagnose patients who do not show clinical signs or symptoms of Leishmaniasis (Moreno, *et al.*, 2006).

Visceral leishmaniasis infections in Canindé approximated the state's epidemiological profile more precisely epidemiological profile, where the city's incidence coefficients remained higher for most of the period (Figure 3). On the other hand, the country's incidence coefficients remained below the others throughout the period from 2011 to 2020, establishing and consolidating the endemic character of the region (BRASIL, 2014).

By analyzing the cases of VL infections in Canindé, it was possible to establish their socio demographic profile more reliably (Table 1). The

most affected age group in this study was 20-59 years (45.3%), followed by 0-9 years (39.6%), with a higher proportion of male cases (75.5%). The relationship between the higher occurrences of VL in males may be related to hormonal factors (Guerra-Silveira, 2013; Cavalcante, 2014).

Studies carried out in the State of Piauí (Chaves *et al.*, 2022) and in the northern region of the State of Bahia (Farias, 2019), which sought to establish the socio demographic profile of the respective regions, corroborated the results found in Canindé, given the similarity of these areas in the proportions by age group, sex and race.

Establishing a relationship between the epidemiological conditions in endemic regions in the northeast of the country, this study sought to estimate the magnitude of the association between the risk factor (RR), living in Canindé between 2011 to 2020, and the outcome attributed to the development of VL and ATL in this period (Table 2). It is noted that, statistically, there is a protective factor related to the development of ATL, due to low rates of notifications of the disease in the Canindé-Ceará and Canindé-Brazil relationship (Paz, 2021).

It is observed that throughout the period, with the exception of 2019, the RR for VL remained above 1 (one) in the Canindé-Brazil correlation, having an average value of 3.93, in other words, individuals living in Canindé were approximately 4 times more likely to develop the disease compared to the national territory.

Figure 3 - Relationship of VL incidence coefficients (per 100,000 inhabitants) between Brazil, Ceará and Canindé-CE, 2011-2020.

Table 1 - Frequencies of socio demographic characteristics of VL cases in residents of Canindé-CE, 2011-2020.

Variables	*N
Age Range	
< 1 year	4/53
1 - 4 years	14/53
5 - 9 years	3/53
10 - 14 years	2/53
15 - 19 years	2/53
20 - 39 years	11/53
40 - 59 years	13/53
60 - 64 years	2/53
65 - 69 years	1/53
70 - 79 years	1/53
Sex	
Male	40/53
Female	13/53
Race	
Brown	48/53
White	1/53
Black	2/53
Ignored	2/53
Residence Zone	
Urban	28/53
Rural	17/53
Peri-urban	2/53
Ignored	6/53

*N, number of cases/ total number of cases

Source: Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINAN); data up to April/2022.

Between the Canindé-Ceará values for VL, there is a 1.4 times greater risk.

In order to consolidate this hypothesis, a statistical calculation was carried out for the confidence index (CI) for $p < 0.05$ (Table 3). Taking into account that there were not significantly enough cases of individuals affected by ATL in Canindé, it was decided to use only the IC values for VL.

In the years of 2011 and 2015, in the Canindé-Ceará relationship, it is noted that the minimum CI value remained greater than 1 (one), being 1.25

Table 2 - Relative risk (RR) of VL and ATL incidence in residents of Canindé-CE, 2011-2020

Ano de notificação	RR (Canindé/Ceará)		RR (Canindé/Brazil)	
	VL	ATL	VL	ATL
2011	2,22*	0,00	7,53	0,00
2012	0,58	0,00	1,59	0,00
2013	0,44	0,23	1,50	0,13
2014	1,39*	0,48	4,91	0,24
2015	2,73*	0,43	8,88	0,26
2016	1,64*	0,35	3,83	0,19
2017	1,42*	0,36	2,98	0,14
2018	0,95	0,36	2,08	0,15
2019	0,37	0,26	0,97	0,16
2020	2,40*	0,23	4,98	0,16
Valor Resultante	1,41	0,27	3,93	0,14

* Values where the RR showed that the risk of developing VL is greater for residents of Canindé compared to the state of Ceará.

Table 3 - Confidence interval (CI) for $p < 0.05$ of VL in residents of Canindé-CE, 2011-2020.

Ano de notificação	CI (Canindé/Ceará)		CI (Canindé/Brazil)	
	CI	CI	CI	CI
2011	1,25	- 3,93*	4,28	- 13,28*
2012	0,15	- 2,34	0,40	- 6,34
2013	0,11	- 1,77	0,38	- 6,00
2014	0,66	- 2,93	2,34	- 10,31*
2015	1,54	- 4,84*	5,04	- 15,65*
2016	0,68	- 3,96	1,59	- 9,21*
2017	0,59	- 3,43	1,24	- 7,17*
2018	0,31	- 2,97	0,67	- 6,46
2019	0,05	- 2,61	0,14	- 6,86
2020	0,89	- 6,47	1,87	- 13,28*

* Values where the CI demonstrated significant differences with the hypothesis that living in Canindé is a risk factor for the development of VL.

and 1.54 respectively, while in the Canindé-Brazil relationship, there were 6 years in which this pattern repeated. These were years in which the RR was significant, i.e. it showed that the sample studied reflected a real effect of the risk factor in the population (Sousa, 2018).

Although the RR of VL in Canindé is higher

compared to both Ceará and Brazil, a relationship cannot be established between living in Canindé and the development of VL for most of the period in Ceará. However, the opposite can be established in relation to Brazil, considering that most of the period, the IC demonstrated significant differences compared to the hypotheses.

CONCLUSION

The data shows that the risk of living in Canindé is only significant when compared to Brazil. In the analysis with the state, although the risk is high, no reliable risk relationship can be established due to the CI values.

It is therefore important that the neglect still existing in relation to VL is reduced, not only because of the seriousness of the disease, but also to ensure greater control of it, with a view to reversing the endemic situation still experienced by the state of Ceará and the municipality of Canindé. Thus, more studies are needed to monitor the epidemiology of Leishmaniasis, as well as greater precision in the data recorded in the databases, which can be achieved by reducing the underreporting of cases and precision in the diagnosis of this disease.

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